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Somatic Embryogenesis and Plant Regeneration from Stem, Leaf, Root and Petal Explants of Sweet Type Carambola (*Averrhoa carambola* L.)

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The effect of different plant growth regulator combinations and concentrations on direct and indirect somatic embryogenesis in *Averrhoa carambola* explants of *in vitro* raised immature and mature *in situ* origin was studied. Percentage response to callus induction from leaf explants of both origin was best on half strength MS medium supplemented with 2 mg/l 2,4-D. Maximum percentage of direct shoot regeneration from leaf explants of *in vitro* origin was on medium with 6 mg/l NAA. NAA at 8 mg/l and 2,4-D at 6 mg/l were equally good for inducing callus on petal explants. Basal stem and root explants of *in vitro* origin cultured on half strength MS medium supplemented with 2 and 4 mg/l BAP respectively produced maximum somatic embryos directly. Mature leaf and petal explants collected from grafted trees failed to produce somatic embryos directly. Embryogenic calli obtained from mature leaves on medium containing 4 mg/l 2,4-D and from petals on medium containing 8 mg/l NAA and also on 6 mg/l 2,4-D were best suited for indirect somatic embryogenesis. Leaf callus produced maximum number of somatic embryoids on medium containing a combination of 1 mg/l ABA and 2.4 mg/l glyphosate. Maximum somatic embryogenesis on petal callus was observed on medium with 2 mg/l ABA and 1.2 mg/l glyphosate. Embryoids produced on medium with glyphosate and ABA were germinated on MS medium with malt extract and GA₃ (0.1 mg/l) or BAP (2 mg/l).

Keywords: *Averrhoa*, callusing, carambola, regeneration, somatic embryogenesis, tissue culture.

Introduction

Carambola (*Averrhoa carambola* L.) is a small, spreading, evergreen tree belonging to the family Oxalidaceae. It is native of South-East Asia and now grown in all tropical and sub-tropical areas of the world. Carambola fruits are rich in reducing sugars, minerals, ascorbic acid and vitamin A. There are two types of carambola, namely, sweet and sour types (Singh, 1986; Ghose and Dhua, 1990). Sweet types, which are commercially viable, are grown in Malaysia, Singapore, Taiwan, Florida, Hawaii, Japan and Australia (Litz and Griffis, 1989). Carambola is highly cross-pollinated and shows a high degree of heterozygosity, which is a constraint for clonal propagation and crop improvement.

Studies on micropropagation in carambola have been attempted and the results have shown its possibility to obtain proliferation of shoots and roots *in vitro*

(Prashanta *et al.*, 2003a). Somatic embryogenesis is a proven method of propagation on a large scale and it is an important tool for genetic manipulations such as somaclonal variations, induced mutations, plant transformations, etc. Somatic embryogenesis is best known as a pathway for induced regeneration *in vitro* occurring either indirectly from callus, cell suspension or protoplast or directly from cells of organised structures.

Materials and methods

Immature leaves and basal stem segments (devoid of any node) from *in vitro* shoot cultures of sweet type carambola maintained in plant tissue culture laboratory and mature leaves and petals from grafted trees maintained at the Division of Horticulture were used as explants. The explants collected from *in situ* plants were washed thoroughly in running tap water and were surface sterilized for half an hour with a solution containing Bavistin 600 mg/l, Centrimide 300 mg/l and Streptomycin 100 mg/l. Treated leaves were rinsed

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with sterile double distilled water for 3–4 times. These explants were then treated with 0.1% HgCl_2 for 2 min. Petals were treated with 0.1% HgCl_2 for 1 min only; as they were found sensitive to any elaborate surface sterilization treatment. These petals and leaves were finally rinsed with sterile double distilled water for 2–3 times to remove the traces of sterilants.

For callus induction, surface sterilized leaf (*in vitro* and *in situ* origin) and petal explants were transferred to half strength MS medium (Murashige and Skoog, 1962) supplemented with different growth regulators such as BAP, 2,4-D and NAA. These growth regulators were used individually at different concentrations (2, 4, 6, 8 or 10 mg/l). Four weeks after culturing, calli induced were analysed and scored depending on growth, texture and colour. No callus induction was attempted from *in vitro*-raised stem and root segments since these explants resulted in direct somatic embryogenesis.

Surface sterilized root and stem explants were directly transferred to half strength MS medium with different levels of BAP; and observations on direct somatic embryogenesis were recorded eight weeks after culture. Calli induced on leaf and petal explants were transferred separately to MS medium containing dif-

ferent combinations of ABA and glyphosate to study the somatic embryogenesis response.

The embryoids induced were cultured on MS and MT (Murashige and Tucker, 1969) media with growth regulators such as BAP, GA_3 and IBA along with malt extract. Shoots regenerated from embryoids were transferred to liquid MS medium with 2 mg/l NAA for root induction. The experiments were laid out using completely randomized design and the data were analysed statistically.

Results and discussion

Induction of callus on leaf explants of in vitro origin

All the growth regulators (2,4-D, NAA and BAP) induced callus on leaf explants when cultured on half strength MS medium with varying degrees of success (Table 1). Direct regeneration of shoots from leaf explants with 40% response was observed on medium with 6.0 mg/l NAA. Concentrations of 2 and 4 mg/l 2,4-D induced good amount of compact, light green callus with 100% response (Figure 1A). However, with a higher concentration of 8 mg/l 2,4-D, the callusing

Table 1. Effect of 2,4-D, NAA and BAP on callus induction and regeneration on immature leaves of *in vitro* origin.

Hormone concentration on half MS medium (mg/l)	Per cent explant response	Callus score (visual)	Kind of callus	Callus colour	Shoot regeneration percentage
Control	0	–	–	–	0
2,4-D					
2.0	100	+++	Compact	Light green	30
4.0	100	++	Compact	Light green	11
6.0	100	++	Friable	White	0
8.0	90	+	Friable	White	0
10.0	90	+	Friable	White	0
NAA					
2.0	90	+++	Compact	Light green	30
4.0	100	+++	Compact	Greenish white	30
6.0	100	+++	Compact	Greenish brown	40
8.0	90	+	Friable	White	0
10.0	80	+	Friable	White	0
BAP					
2.0	70	+	Friable	White	0
4.0	100	++	Friable to compact	Light green	20
6.0	100	+	Friable	Light green	0

Observations were recorded four weeks after culture. Number of replications per treatment = ten.

–, No callus production; +, poor callus; ++, good callus; +++, very good callus.

Figure 1A–F. Callus induction, somatic embryogenesis, embryo germination and rooting in carambola. A, Proliferation of compact and light green callus and shoot regeneration on leaf explants of *in vitro* origin on half strength MS medium with 2 mg/l 2,4-D (four weeks after culture); B, Healthy embryogenic callus induced on leaf explants of mature origin with 4 mg/l 2,4-D; C, Compact, light green callus induced on petal explants with 8 mg/l NAA; D, Stages of direct somatic embryo development observed on basal stem segments with BAP at 2 mg/l; E, Globular somatic embryos induced on swollen basal stem segments of immature origin with 2 mg/l BAP. Cotyledonary stages of embryo developing into a shoot can be observed; F, Somatic embryogenesis on *in vitro* root explants on MS media with 1(a), 2(b) and 5(c) mg/l BAP.

response was reduced and the callus induced was white. Similar kind of callusing response from cotyledon explants of *in vitro* origin was observed in rose-apple when supra optimal levels of 2,4-D reduced the callus proliferation (Prashanta *et al.*, 2003b). BAP and

NAA at 4 and 6 mg/l induced cent per cent callusing and callus was greenish white. Callus obtained from NAA medium was compact but that from BAP medium was friable to compact at these concentrations. Even after eight weeks of culture, all growth regulators failed

Table 2. Effect of 2,4-D and NAA on callus induction from petals and leaves of mature origin.

Hormone concentration (mg/l)	Per cent explant response		Callus score		Kind of callus		Colour of callus	
	Petals	Leaves	Petal callus	Leaf callus	Petal callus	Leaf callus	Petal callus	Leaf callus
Control	0	0	-	-				
2,4-D								
2.0	0	100	-	++		Compact		Light green
4.0	0	90	-	+++		Compact to friable		Light green
6.0	50	90	+++	+	Compact to friable	Friable	White	White
8.0	30	50	++	+	Friable	Friable	White	White
10.0	20	0	+	-	Friable		White	
NAA								
2.0	0	0	-	-				
4.0	0	0	-	-				
6.0	0	0	-	-				
8.0	50	0	+++	-	Compact		Light green	
10.0	50	0	++	-	Friable		Whitish green	

Observations were recorded four weeks after culture. Number of replications per treatment = ten.

-, No callus production; +, poor callus; ++ good callus; +++, very good callus.

to induce direct somatic embryogenesis from immature leaf explants.

Induction of callus from mature leaf explants of in situ origin

Among the different growth regulators tried, only 2,4-D induced callus on mature leaves (Table 2). This callus was embryogenic, compact and light green. Maximum proliferation was obtained on medium with 4 mg/l 2,4-D (Figure 1B). With increase in concentration of 2,4-D, percentage callus induction was reduced and callus was white in colour.

Successful induction of callus from tree crops has been done mainly using 2,4-D. Prashanta *et al.* (2003) noted 2,4-D as the most efficient auxin in callus induction from all kinds of explants of roseapple which is in agreement with the present results.

Callus induction from petal explants

In case of petals, high concentration of auxins such as 2,4-D and NAA induced callusing (Table 2). BAP failed to induce callusing at all concentrations (2–10 mg/l). Compact to friable white callus was induced on medium with 6 mg/l 2,4-D. In case of NAA, higher concentration of 8 mg/l was needed to induce compact and light green callus (Figure 1C).

Direct somatic embryogenesis

Direct somatic embryogenesis from in vitro raised stem explants. Basal internodal stem segments of seedling origin when cultured on half strength MS media supplemented with BAP at different concentrations gave rise to somatic embryos (Table 3). All stages of somatic embryos were isolated from the cultures (Figure 1D). Maximum number of globular embryoids (16.0) was recorded at the concentration of 2 mg/l of BAP (Figure 1E) and percentage response was highest (100). Number of embryoids induced was significantly higher compared with that at concentrations of 4 and 6 mg/l BAP. In treatments without BAP also, embryogenesis was observed; but the number of embryoids recorded was significantly lesser than that obtained with BAP at 2 mg/l.

Direct somatic embryogenesis from in vitro raised root explants. Root explants cultured on half strength MS medium supplemented with different levels (2, 4 and 6 mg/l) of BAP resulted in direct somatic embryogenesis. Greenish and yellowish embryoids were first observed six weeks after inoculation and observations were recorded two weeks after embryogenesis. Eight weeks after culture at 4 mg/l BAP, maximum average number of embryos (6 per explant) was recorded (Figure 1F, Table 3). With increase in BAP concentration up to 6 mg/l, there was a significant decrease in the number of embryos (3.0) proliferated. Immature

Table 3. Effect of BAP concentration on direct somatic embryogenesis on immature basal stem and root explants of *in vitro* origin (8 weeks after culture).

BAP concentration (mg/l)	Per cent explant response		Mean number of somatic embryos per explant	
	Basal stem	Root	Basal stem	Root
Control	70	0	4.0 ^c	0.00 ^d
2.0	100	100	16.0 ^a	5.00 ^b
4.0	50	100	6.2 ^b	6.00 ^a
6.0	30	100	4.6 ^c	3.00 ^c
CD at 5%			2.46	0.12
SEm ±			1.74	0.04

Number of replications per treatment = ten.

^{a-d}Means within each column followed by the same script are not significantly different by Student's *t*-test at 0.05 probability level.

Table 4. Effect of ABA and glyphosate on induction of somatic embryoids on petal callus induced on 8 mg/l NAA and 6 mg/l 2,4-D media and leaf callus induced on 4 mg/l 2,4-D.

Treatment combinations	Kind of response		Mean no. of embryoids/explant on				
			Per cent response		Petal callus from		Leaf callus from
	Petal callus	Leaf callus	Petal callus	Leaf callus	8 mg/l NAA medium	6 mg/l 2, 4-D medium	4 mg/l 2, 4-D medium
Control	Callus turned brown and proliferated	Callus turned brown and proliferated	100	100	80.0 ^e	94.2 ^c	90.2 ^a
ABA (1 mg/l) + glyphosate (1.2 mg/l)	"	"	100	100	29.0 ^e	112.2 ^b	32.2 ^d
ABA (2 mg/l) + glyphosate (1.2 mg/l)	"	"	100	100	159.0 ^a	162.0 ^a	52.4 ^b
ABA (3 mg/l) + glyphosate (1.2 mg/l)	"	"	100	100	91.4 ^b	87.0 ^d	23.6 ^e
ABA (1 mg/l) + glyphosate (2.4 mg/l)	"	"	100	100	55.20 ^d	69.6 ^e	91.4 ^a
ABA (2 mg/l) + glyphosate (2.4 mg/l)	"	"	100	100	23.4 ^f	67.6 ^e	44.8 ^c
ABA (3 mg/l) + glyphosate (2.4 mg/l)	"	"	0	0	00.0 ^g	00.0 ^f	0.0 ^f
CD @ 5%					4.75	5.80	5.39
SEm ±					3.36	3.98	3.81

Number of replications per treatment = five.

^{a-d}Means within each column followed by the same script are not significantly different by Student's *t*-test at 0.05 probability level. Observations were recorded four weeks after culture.

roots are already proved as good explants for direct regeneration of tree species such as kiwifruit (Kumar and Sharma, 2001). Leaf and petal explants failed to respond to direct somatic embryogenesis.

Indirect somatic embryogenesis

Indirect somatic embryogenesis from callus induced from mature leaf explants. The embryogenic calli obtained from leaves on medium containing 4 mg/l

2,4-D were transferred to media containing different concentrations of ABA and glyphosate combinations. It was observed that leaf callus produced maximum number of embryoids (91.4 per explant) on medium containing a combination of 1 mg/l of ABA and 2.4 mg/l glyphosate (Table 4). Mature explants from trees usually fail to respond to direct somatic embryogenesis. Induction of callus from these explants and further use in somatic embryogenesis is a viable alternative (Iyer and Gopinath, 2000).

Figure 2A–C. Callus induction, somatic embryogenesis, embryo germination and rooting in carambola. A, Somatic embryogenesis from petal-derived callus, four weeks after culture on medium with 2 mg/l ABA and 1.2 mg/l glyphosate; B, Proliferation of callus and shoot regeneration from embryoid when transferred on MS medium with 0.1 mg/l GA₃ and 2 mg/l BAP; C, Rooting of micro cuttings on liquid MS medium with 2 mg/l NAA (6 weeks after culture).

Indirect somatic embryogenesis from callus induced on petal explants. The embryogenic petal calli induced on 8 mg/l NAA and also on 6 mg/l 2,4-D produced maximum number of embryoids (162 per explant) on medium containing a combination of 2 mg/l ABA and 1.2 mg/l glyphosate (Table 4, Figure 2A). Petal calli induced on 2,4-D media were superior over calli from NAA media with respect to their somatic embryogenesis capacity. This superiority of 2,4-D over NAA on induction of somatic embryos is in agreement with the findings of Shankhdhar *et al.* (2002).

Indirect somatic embryogenesis was more frequently observed than direct embryogenesis and it has been accomplished with a wide array of explants. In this study, somatic embryoids were produced on callus obtained from mature leaf and petal explants, when transferred onto the medium supplemented with ABA and glyphosate in combination. ABA in combination

with auxin or cytokinin has been used for induction of somatic embryos by Deng *et al.* (1991) and Chen and Chen (1992). However studies at Tuskegee University have indicated that ABA in combination with glyphosate have increased embryo production by any folds in sweet potato (*Ipomoea batatas* L.) compared with glyphosate or ABA alone (Gowda and Prakash, 1996). Somatic embryoids produced on leaf callus was maximum on medium supplemented with a combination of 1 mg/l ABA and 2.4 mg/l glyphosate and with petal callus there were maximum number (162.0) of embryoids produced on medium supplemented with 2 mg/l ABA and 1.2 mg/l glyphosate (Table 4). Generally speaking, the petal callus obtained from 2,4-D source gave increased response for somatic embryo production when subcultured. The somatic embryogenesis response was comparatively less on callus obtained from NAA source since the callus from 2,4-D media proliferated more quickly on somatic embryo production

media compared to callus obtained from media containing NAA.

Germination of embryoids and rooting of shoots

Embryoids obtained from different experiments were randomly selected and transferred to MS and MT media with malt extract containing different growth regulators such as BAP, IBA and GA₃. The embryoids on all the plant growth regulators except IBA produced callus first and later gave rise to secondary embryoids. With IBA, only callusing was observed and was not necessary for embryoid germination. In the treatment comprising MS media with GA₃ (0.1 mg/l) and BAP (2.0 mg/l), proliferation of callus from the base of the cultured embryoids and regeneration of shootlets was observed (Figure 2B). Treatments with all the three growth regulators (BAP, IBA and GA₃) resulted in excess callus growth with no shoot proliferation. Separated shoot micro cuttings were rooted six weeks after transfer on MS medium supplemented with 2 mg/l NAA (Figure 2C).

This study offers a guideline for *in vitro* propagation of *Averrhoa carambola* L. This species showed good response for callus proliferation, somatic embryogenesis and regeneration especially when the explants used are immature or of *in vitro* origin. This potential species especially of sweet type can be commercially exploited for mass multiplication and propagation. Further our regeneration protocols could well be exploited for crop improvement via genetic manipulations.

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